

Postgermination growth and ethylene production of rice at 2 and 21% O₂^a

O ₂ concn. (%)	Variety ^b	C ₂ H ₄ ^c (ppm)			Elongation ^d (mm/3 d)		
		1	2	3	Coleoptile	Root	Leaf
2	Control	0.18 a	0.11 a	0.12 a	12.5 a	1.6 a	0.0 a
	Tolerant	0.15 a	0.07 a	0.10 a	24.1 c	1.5 a	0.0 a
21	Control	0.56 b	0.62 b	0.54 b	15.6 b	11.0 b	5.7 b
	Tolerant	0.64 c	1.03 c	0.89 c	26.2 d	19.0 c	5.7 b

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bControl varieties = IR8, IR36, IR50, IR74, tolerant varieties = CO 25, ASD1, JC178, Taotabi. ^cEthylene concentration in the flask at 1, 2, and 3 d after start of incubation. ^dMeasured after start of incubation.

Taotabi (13746, India) and controls, IR8, IR36, IR50, and IR74.

A completely randomized design with three replications was used. Pregerminated seeds were placed in 25-ml Erlenmeyer flasks (35 seeds/flask), and incubated in 2 or 21% O₂ for 3 d. The CO₂ produced by the seeds during incubation was absorbed by 20% potassium hydroxide in a vial placed inside the flask. We measured the

ethylene concentration in the flask every day to estimate endogenous ethylene production.

Seedling growth was retarded in 2% O₂ (see table). Root and leaf elongation and endogenous ethylene production were less in 2% O₂ than in 21% O₂.

The coleoptiles of tolerant varieties elongated more than those of control varieties at 2% O₂. Because the endogenous ethylene production did not

differ among varieties, other factors that were not studied might have caused the varietal difference in coleoptile elongation.

The tolerant varieties grew better and had longer roots and coleoptiles than the control varieties, even in 21% O₂. The tolerant varieties also produced more ethylene than did the control varieties.

It is known that standing water in ricefields contains dissolved O₂ from the atmosphere, while flooded soil has little O₂. A seed germinating under anaerobic conditions in the soil must get O₂ by raising the tip of its coleoptile above the soil surface. The seed that fails to get O₂ will not develop roots and leaves, and will eventually die. The superiority of tolerant varieties in coleoptile elongation might be the reason why they are excellent for seedling establishment in flooded soil. This varietal trait could be used in breeding programs aimed to develop suitable varieties for direct seeding. ■

Root characteristics of rice genotypes with different drought responses

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Drought resistance has been associated with crop root characters. Drought-resistant upland rices have few but thick roots that penetrate deep layers during soil drying.

To evaluate the contribution of root characteristics to drought resistance, rice genotypes that differed in response to vegetative drought (as determined in previous field studies) were grown under well-watered upland field conditions and in an aeroponic system in a phytotron glasshouse (70% relative humidity, 29/21 °C day/night temperature) at IRRI.

Root number, root length, and root diameter were measured on 45-d-old plants of eight genotypes grown in the aeroponic system. The root system was divided into four portions: u = upper, um = upper middle, dm = deeper-middle,

Root characteristics of rice genotypes with different drought responses in aeroponic and field experiments.

Genotype	Drought response	Roots (no./plant)	Root diameter ^a (mm)				Total root length
			Upper	Upper-middle	Deeper-middle	Distal	
<i>Aeroponics</i>							
IR30716-B-1-B-6	Susceptible	36	0.99	0.91	0.78	0.65	33.4
IRAT 9	Susceptible	44	0.87	0.81	0.68	0.53	34.6
IR20	Susceptible	50	0.59	0.53	0.47	0.41	29.9
UPLRi-5	Moderately tolerant	35	0.95	0.89	0.73	0.58	49.5
Kinandang Patong	Moderately tolerant	33	1.04	0.99	0.87	0.75	50.0
IR43	Moderately tolerant	49	0.84	0.74	0.66	0.55	38.3
IR10120-72-1-4	Tolerant	45	1.10	1.02	0.91	0.79	55.1
IR9560-2-6-3-1	Tolerant	35	0.95	0.81	0.73	0.59	54.9
	LSD 0.05	12	0.09	0.15	0.13	0.18	4.7
<i>Field</i>							
IR20	Susceptible	-	0.74	0.60	0.52	0.38	6.2
Kinandang Patong	Moderately tolerant	-	1.13	1.05	0.91	0.73	5.4
IR47686-6-1-2	Tolerant	-	1.23	1.11	0.92	0.83	5.6
	LSD 0.05	-	0.06	0.06	0.09	0.13	2.3

^aRoot diameter measured in four parts of roots in aeroponically grown plants and in four soil layers for field-grown plants.

Root diameter of IR20 and Kinandang Patong in aeroponics and field experiments.

genotypes were sampled at 33 d after emergence to determine root diameter and total root length. Roots were collected from four replications from depths of 0-0.1, 0.1-0.2, 0.2-0.3, and 0.3-0.4 m using a monolith soil sampler (0.20 × 0.20 × 0.40 m³). Roots were washed and diameter was measured for 25-50 root segments from a random sample of 10 primary axes from each layer. Total root length was measured with an optical scanner for all roots on all layers.

Root number was not associated with drought response nor with root diameter

and *d* = distal. Twenty-five segments from each of the portions were laid on a flat surface and their widths measured with a micrometer to estimate root diameter.

Roots of field-grown plants of three

(see table). Root diameter was greatest in drought-tolerant and least in susceptible lines or cultivars. Total root length under aeroponics appeared to be greater for drought-tolerant than for drought-susceptible rice genotypes, but the same was not true under field conditions.

Our observations, although confined to only a few lines and cultivars, confirm results of previous aeroponic studies on drought resistance, which also involved only a few genotypes. Root thickness is a relatively stable character; hence, there was high correlation ($r = 0.97^{**}$) between root diameter measured in aeroponic- and field-grown rice (see figure). Thus it is possible to select for root thickness under aeroponics. As the trait also appeared to be related to drought response, aeroponic evaluation of root diameter may assist in selecting drought-tolerant rice genotypes. ■

Fertilizer management—inorganic sources

Response to P of some rice varieties in Assam, India

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We evaluated the performance of IR8, Jaya, Monoharsali, and Mahsuri at different P levels.

The soil is acidic with pH 5.5 (1:2 glass electrode method), sandy loam texture, 0.6% N (Kjeldahl method), 7 kg P/ha (Brays and Kurtz No. 1), and 65 kg K/ha (neutral ammonium acetate

method). We applied 0, 8.8, 17.6, and 26 kg P/ha basally as single superphosphate, 40 kg N/ha as urea, and 17 kg K/ha as muriate of potash. The experiment was laid out in a factorial randomized complete block design with three replications. We used the Vanado molybdate method to measure P uptake by plants at maturity.

Monoharsali yielded the most grain (Table 1). Grain yield of all varieties significantly increased as P increased.

Mahsuri was tallest with 26 kg P/ha, and IR8 had the heaviest roots. P uptake

was greatest at 26 kg P/ha; it decreased as P decreased (Table 2).

P fertilizer-use efficiencies were 24.0, 21.8, and 18.8 kg grain/kg P applied at 8.8, 17.6, and 26 kg/ha. P-uptake efficiency decreased as fertilization increased. This might be due to the equilibrium effect of 40 kg N/ha and 17 kg K/ha. The correlation between grain yield and P uptake was highly significant ($r = 0.85^{**}$), indicating that P uptake influenced yield. ■

Table 1. Interaction of variety and P level on yield of some rice varieties in Assam, India.

P level (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)				
	IR8	Jaya	Monoharsali	Mahsuri	Mean
0	2.6	2.7	3.1	3.0	2.9
8.8	3.0	3.1	3.8	3.5	3.3
17.6	3.3	3.4	4.1	4.0	3.7
26	3.4	3.7	4.3	4.5	4.0
Mean	3.1	3.2	3.8	3.8	—
LSD (0.05)	V = 0.1	P = 0.1	V × P = 0.45		

Table 2. Effect of P on several characters of some rice varieties. Assam, India.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Root weight (g/m ²)	P uptake (kg/ha)
<i>Variety</i>			
IR8	91.99	180.80	36.99
Jaya	100.04	113.53	44.62
Monoharsali	111.13	114.65	48.35
Mahsuri	112.73	117.37	49.53
LSD (0.05)	0.83	4.31	0.84
<i>P level (kg/ha)</i>			
0	100.29	84.76	32.16
8.8	101.55	104.27	43.90
17.6	105.08	129.93	48.29
26	108.96	135.38	55.13
LSD (0.05)	0.86	4.31	0.84